

Supplementary material for

Lipids in photosynthetic protein complexes in the thylakoid membrane of plants, algae, and cyanobacteria

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Supplementary Fig. S1. Lipid-binding sites in the PSI complexes from (A) *Bryopsis corticulans*, (B) *Chlorella ohadii*, (C) *Dunaliella salina*, (D) *Cyanidioschyzon merolae* strain 10D, and (E) *Chaetoceros gracilis*. Top views from the stromal side are shown for each complex. Lipid molecules are shown as colored spheres, with oxygen atoms in red. Protein backbones are shown as silver cartoons and pigments and other cofactors are omitted for clarity. Data are from PDB ID 6IGZ for *B. corticulans* (Qin *et al.*, 2019), 6ZZX for *C. ohadii* (Caspary *et al.*, 2021), 6SL5 for *D. salina* (Caspary *et al.*, 2020), 5ZGB for *C. merolae* strain 10 D (Pi *et al.*, 2018), and 6LY5 for *C. gracilis* (Xu *et al.*, 2020).

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Supplementary Fig. S2. Lipid-binding sites in the PSII complexes from (A) *Cyanidium caldarium* and (B) *Chaetoceros gracilis*. Top views from the stromal side are shown for each complex. Lipid molecules are shown as colored spheres, with oxygen atoms in red. Protein backbones are shown as silver cartoons and pigments and other cofactors are omitted for clarity. Data are from PDB ID 4YUU for *C. caldarium* (Ago *et al.*, 2016) and 6JLU for *C. gracilis* (Pi *et al.*, 2019).

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